

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIALS

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Hydrodynamic Performance of a Bio-Inspired Modular Platform for Coral Reef Rehabilitation

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S1- Numerical modelling methods

1. Theoretical background

For similar coral reef and porous marine structure studies, RANS- and VRANS-based numerical frameworks are commonly adopted as practical and reliable approaches for wave–structure interaction analysis (Fang et al., 2022; Yao et al., 2020, 2022; Zhou and Ye, 2022). Although Large Eddy Simulation (LES) can provide higher-fidelity resolution of instantaneous coherent vortices, it requires significantly finer meshes and substantially higher computational cost, particularly for geometrically complex multi-body porous systems and long-duration wave simulations. Therefore, the present study employs a validated RANS-based framework as a practical engineering approach for comparative hydraulic assessment rather than turbulence-model development. Similar applications of RANS-based modeling for identifying large-scale recirculation behavior of flow responses have also been successfully reported in previous studies (Mohammadian et al., 2020; Rizzi, 2023; Robinson et al., 2016). In this regard, an open-source software with C++ programming potential called OpenFOAM® version 2406 was deployed. This software incorporated Finite Volume Method (FVM) as the base approach for solving partial differential equations. OpenFOAM uses several distinct solvers for simulating various problems. Among all, the *interFOAM* solver was selected (Higuera et al., 2013a, b). It can simulate the transient flow with two incompressible, isothermal, and immiscible fluids. Note that, the governing equations are solved for the two-phase mixture flow. The solver effectively accommodates regular and irregular wave patterns, leveraging static or dynamic mesh configurations.

The main governing equations, i.e., continuity and momentum equations, are (Fu et al., 2025):

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{U}) = 0 \quad (\text{S1})$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho U)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho U U) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot (\tau + \tau_t) + \rho g + f_\sigma \quad (\text{S2})$$

where U is the fluid velocity, t denotes time, ρ is the fluid density, g denotes the gravitational acceleration, p is the pressure, and f_σ is the surface tension (Miyazaki et al., 2018). Also, τ and τ_t are molecular (viscous) stress tensor and turbulent (Reynolds) stress tensor, which is modeled by Boussinesq hypothesis, respectively (Miyazaki et al., 2018). Due to the necessity of modeling the water-air interface for simulating the wave trains, it is crucial to consider the multiphase basis, theory:

$$\rho = \alpha\rho_1 + (1-\alpha)\rho_2 \quad (S3)$$

Where α acts as an indicator to capture air-flow, thus it is 1 where fluid with density ρ_1 exists, and zero where fluid with density ρ_2 exists. More details regarding the numerical model can be found in (Weller et al., 1998).

2. Vortex structures and visualizations

The RANS Modeling pursues time averaging from parameters like velocity and pressure (Breuer et al., 2003). Consequently, instantaneous eddies and fine-scale turbulent vortex structures cannot be directly resolved with the same fidelity as LES or DNS. Therefore, in the present study, the objective was not to quantitatively resolve instantaneous turbulence structures, but rather to investigate the mean hydrodynamic response adjacent to the bio-mimetic pillars. Note that, identifying eddies and circulation patterns directly from raw numerical contours is not always straightforward. In this regard, supplementary post-processing visualization tools are necessary to better interpret the flow dynamics adjacent to the structure. For this reason, in the current study, Line Integral Convolution (LIC) was applied to the simulation results to trace streamline directions and identify dominant flow patterns (Han et al., 2016). In this approach, the pixel value is computed through a weighted averaging process, where the weighting variable is defined by a convolution kernel. Image convolution synthesizes textures that reveal underlying flow patterns (Shen and Bryson, 1997). To gain a comprehensive understanding of the flow patterns in a three-dimensional state, 3D-stream

traces were also employed. This technique was successfully deployed for the visualization of vortex structures adjacent to a mimetic sponge carried out by (Hashempour and Kolahdoozan, 2024b) and for a rigid finite-height cylinder by (Palau-Salvador et al., 2010). In this method, the detection of complex flow topographies, including spirals, re-circulation bubbles, both downwash and upwash phenomena, and flow separations are possible (Palau-Salvador et al., 2010), while remaining consistent with the time-averaged nature of the RANS framework.

S2 – Numerical Modeling Setup

For simulating the realistic hydraulic conditions, applying appropriate boundary conditions is essential. *no-slip* was used for the channel bottom and sponges' walls. This boundary condition assumes that the speed of the fluid layer in direct contact with the boundary is identical to the velocity of this boundary. As there are no relative movements between fluid and structure surface, this boundary condition is appropriate (Rapp, 2017). Wave velocity boundary conditions were applied at the channel inlet to generate regular waves corresponding to the prescribed wave height and period, while active wave absorption was implemented at the outlet boundary to minimize reflected waves and simulate the function of a physical wave absorber. These conditions were used to reproduce the wavemaker and wave absorber behavior of laboratory wave flumes (Troch and De Rouck, 1999). Moreover, the *free-slip* condition was assigned to the channel walls, in order to minimize artificial lateral wall friction and to better represent an idealized wide-flume condition. To simulate the suction and pumping functions of the sponge, the hydraulic effect was represented through boundary conditions rather than by explicitly modeling a mechanical pump. A *FlowRateInletVelocity* boundary condition was applied at the sponge perforations to impose a constant suction discharge, while a *fixedValue* boundary condition was assigned at the top opening (osculum) to represent the pumping outlet. Since the perforations were distributed around the curved sponge body, prescribing flow rate was considered more practical and physically consistent than assigning a uniform inlet velocity for each individual pore.

Vital parameters like time step, run time, write interval, and courant number were constant for all simulations. The time step was set to *adjustableTimeStep* and according to the simulation log file, the mean courant number remained below 0.05, ensuring numerical stability, as also confirmed by Larsen et al. (2019). The write interval, which determines how frequently simulation data are saved, was set to 0.14 seconds to align with experimental observations. Finally, the total simulation time was set to 40 seconds to account for wave propagation, velocity convergence, and vortex formation. The temporal discretization was performed using the *Euler* scheme, which provides first-order

accuracy in time and was selected to improve numerical stability for free-surface wave simulations. For spatial discretization, gradient terms were calculated using the *Gauss linear* scheme, while the momentum convection term, was discretized using *Gauss linearUpwind grad(U)*, which provides second-order spatial accuracy for the velocity field. For interface capturing in the VOF formulation, the volume fraction transport term was solved using the bounded *vanLeer* scheme and the turbulence transport equations for k and ω were discretized using the *upwind* scheme. The Laplacian terms were treated using *Gauss linear orthogonal*, and interpolation was performed using the *linear* scheme. Therefore, the present model employed a combination of first- and second-order discretization schemes to achieve a suitable balance between numerical accuracy, interface stability, and computational robustness for wave–structure interaction simulations.

S3 - Mesh generation

The computational domain is comprised of two major sections: channel and pillar. Due to the presence of complex pillar geometries and multiple perforated sponge elements, unstructured local refinement was required near the pillars, while the main channel was discretized using a structured and uniform mesh. The main channel had 6 m (length) \times 0.5 m (width) \times 0.4 m (height) dimensions and consisted of cells with 0.03 m (length) \times 0.008 m (width) \times 0.008 m (height) sizes. The design and gridding were performed by the *blockMesh* dictionary of OpenFOAM V. 2406. To better capture the velocity gradients and local flow interactions around the bio-mimetic sponge elements, local refinement was performed using *SnappyHexMesh*. Surface refinement was applied to the sponge geometry with refinement level (2 2), while sharper geometric edges and small-scale features were further resolved using explicit feature-edge refinement with level 3. In addition, `nCellsBetweenLevels = 2` was adopted to ensure a gradual transition between refined and coarser cells, improving mesh quality and numerical stability. The near-wall mesh resolution was evaluated using the dimensionless wall distance parameter (z^+). The representative z^+ values were ≈ 31 for the channel bed and 37 for the lateral channel walls, which fall within the recommended range for wall-function-based turbulence treatment. According to Salim and Cheah (2009), values of z^+ close to the lower bound of the logarithmic wall region ($z^+ \approx 30$) are considered desirable for accurate wall-function implementation.

To achieve an appropriate balance between numerical accuracy and computational efficiency, a mesh-independence analysis was performed using six computational meshes with progressively increasing cell numbers. The percentage difference (Eq. S4) was employed to identify the optimum mesh by comparing the mean velocity and turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) obtained from two consecutive mesh resolutions. The analysis was conducted at two representative locations: one downstream of the pillar patch ($X/D = 4$, $Y/D = 0$), where wake formation dominates the wave-induced flow, and one upstream ($X/D = -50$, $Y/D = 0$), representing the incoming wave field. Mesh

independence was considered to be achieved when the percentage difference between two consecutive meshes was below the predefined threshold of 5%.

$$Percentage\ Difference = \frac{|x_i - x_{i+1}|}{\left(\frac{x_i + x_{i+1}}{2}\right)} \times 100 \quad (S4)$$

where x_i and x_{i+1} are the averaged magnitude velocities or TKE for scenarios i and $i+1$, respectively.

Fig.S1 reports the results. It should be noted that the reported cell sizes correspond only to the background channel mesh defined in the *blockMesh* dictionary.

Fig. S1. Mesh-independence analysis based on percentage differences between consecutive meshes:

(a) mean velocity at $X/D = 4$ and $Y/D = 0$, (b) mean velocity at $X/D = -50$ and $Y/D = 0$, (c) TKE at $X/D = 4$ and $Y/D = 0$, and (d) TKE at $X/D = -50$ and $Y/D = 0$

As shown in Fig. S1, Cases containing more than 7.1×10^5 cells, satisfy the proposed mesh-independence criterion, with percentage differences below the predefined threshold of 5% for almost all comparisons. The only exception is the TKE profile at $X/D = 4$ and $Y/D = 0$, where the

percentage difference is approximately 6%. This location corresponds to the immediate wake region downstream of the pillar patch, where re-circulation bubbles and rapidly evolving turbulent structures make TKE particularly sensitive to mesh resolution. Considering that the deviation is small and confined to this highly unsteady region, the mesh was considered sufficiently independent for the objectives of the present study.

To achieve a suitable compromise between computational cost and numerical accuracy, Case 3 was selected as the optimum mesh. This mesh adequately resolves the dominant hydrodynamic structures visualized using SurfaceLIC and three-dimensional stream traces while maintaining a reasonable computational expense. The selected simulation required approximately 60 h of computation on a workstation equipped with 23 logical CPU cores.

S4. Validation of the numerical model

To achieve reliable data from simulations, validation by physical experiment is essential. For this reason, experimental data from physical modeling conducted by (Hashempour and Kolahdoozan, 2024a) was considered. In this program, first, a mimetic sponge was designed and made. This device had two concentric perforated cylindrical bodies, and pores were connected to each other by elastic narrow pipes. Moreover, to simulate the suction/pumping function, a submersible pump was placed inside the inner cylinder. Fig. S2 shows the laboratory version of apparatus.

Fig. S2. The mimetic sponge: (a) side-view of structure, (b) plan-view and pumping effects, and (c) schematic draw of the mimetic sponge including: 1. Outer cylinder, 2. Inner cylinder, 3. Cone transition, 4. Bottom cover, 5. Submersible pump, and 6. Elastic pipe

It should be noted that the body had 0.08m diameter and a height of 0.2 m. The suction/pumping discharge was 300 Lit/hr and lateral pores had 0.004 m diameter.

Experiments were carried out in a rectangular channel with 12 m (length) \times 0.3 m (width) \times 0.4 m (height) in the hydraulics laboratory of the Amirkabir University of Technology, Tehran, Iran. A flap type wavemaker with motor power of 1400 rpm was placed upstream, which made regular waves with H of 0.053 m and a period of 1.3 sec. Water elevation and velocity were measured by UC500 ultrasonic sensors and Acoustic Doppler Velocimeter (ADV) respectively. ADV was placed in three stations, and measuring was performed at five vertical points: 0.01 m, 0.04 m, 0.07 m, 0.10 m, and 0.13 m. Two of the velocity measurement stations were located at the same upstream and downstream positions as the wave gauges, following the Mansard and Funke (1980) theory, in order to evaluate both wave and velocity characteristics at consistent reference locations. In addition, one ADV station was positioned at a distance of one body diameter (1D) from the sponge body, corresponding to the main bluff-body influence zone where wake development, vortex generation, and momentum exchange are strongest. This location follows the recommendation of Palau-Salvador et al. (2010) for identifying local hydrodynamic effects around bluff bodies.

The ultrasonic sensors were installed at the top of the flume for water-elevation measurements. Their locations were selected based on the Mansard and Funke (1980) theory, where the sensors should be placed approximately one wavelength away from the reflective structure to minimize wave reflection interference and improve the accuracy of incident and reflected wave decomposition. Accordingly, one sensor was located upstream to capture the undisturbed incident wave, one was intentionally positioned above the sponge region to evaluate local free-surface behavior, and the third sensor was placed one wavelength downstream of the sponge to evaluate transmitted wave conditions. Fig. S3 illustrates the setup of physical experiments configuration.

Fig. S3. (a) Rectangular channel, ADV, and ultrasonic sensor (b) Schematic draw of experimental setup

Water elevation and phase averaged velocity for both physical and numerical simulations are illustrated in Fig. S4.

Fig. S4. Results of validation of water elevation and velocity in: (a, d, and g) station 1, (b, e, and h) station 2, and (c, f, and i) station 3

The RMSE for water elevation is less than 0.01 m, and the R^2 value exceed 0.85, indicating that the model's accuracy is satisfactory. Moreover, results show that RMSE and R^2 for velocity is less than 0.008 m/s and over 0.85, respectively. Therefore, model work accurate for capturing water elevation and velocity. Note that a minor discrepancy occurred for water elevation at station 2 due to the sensor's positioning. Fig. S3 illustrates that the ultrasonic sensor at this station is positioned directly above the sponge; hence, wave disturbances result in discrepancies between the measured and simulated data.

In addition to the statistical measurement, the model successfully reproduced the overall hydrodynamic trends observed in the laboratory, including the free-surface response and the vertical distribution of velocity throughout the water column. This aspect is particularly important because the principal conclusions of the present study are based on comparative changes in wave propagation behavior and mean phase velocity among different pillar configurations. Furthermore,

numerical results were extracted only after the initial transient stage had disappeared and the wave field reached a stable periodic condition. Therefore, the combined agreement in free-surface elevation and velocity distribution provides confidence in the capability of the numerical framework to predict the mean hydrodynamic behavior of the bio-mimetic pillar configurations investigated in this study.

It should be noted that the validation was performed for mean flow behavior and free-surface response; flow structures such as recirculation bubbles, vortex rings, and spiral vortices were interpreted qualitatively using SurfaceLIC and 3D stream traces rather than through direct experimental vortex measurements.

S5- Visualization by SurfaceLIC and 3D-stream traces

1. SurfaceLIC at x-y plane

Hamilton et al. (2025) used physical experiments to show how waves can enhance the connection of corals within a canopy through a “pumping and trapping” mechanism in re-circulation bubbles (RB), stagnation lines (SL), and stagnation points (SP). This issue was clearly observed via image processing technique (SurfaceLIC) in the numerical simulation of the current study (Fig. S5).

Fig. S5. SurfaceLIC plots for the region $-2.5 \leq X/D \leq 10$, $Z/h = 0.03$, and $-4 \leq Y/D \leq 4$: T1 at (a) $3T/10$, (b) $7T/10$, (c) $8T/10$, R1 at (d) $3T/10$, (e) $7T/10$, (f) $8T/10$, and C1 at (g) $3T/10$, (h) $7T/10$, and (i) $8T/10$.

Fig. S5 depicts vortex structures at the XY plane ($Z/h = 0.03$) at various time steps: $3T/10$, $7T/10$, and $8T/10$. To ensure the detection of vortex structures, it is essential to capture images near the bed, as reported by Palau-Salvador et al. (2010); thus, all pictures are prepared at $Z/h = 0.03$.

As can be observed, various sponge configurations in a pillar engender complex circulation patterns. Detection of these patterns is essential, as freshwater parcels and nutrients are trapped in RBs and remain in circular orbits for much longer than they take to pass through the internal channels of coral. This process can influence nutrient transport and zooplankton retention, potentially affecting coral colony health and growth (Chang et al. 2009). The main feature difference among the various configurations is the forms of RBs. At $3T/10$, as the pitch-to-diameter ratio (P/D) for T1 and R1 is 2, in the intermediate range, the side-by-side sponges interact. In this condition, asymmetric RBs and deflected flow (DF) emerge. This is also observed for side-by-side finite-height cylinders (Afgan et al. 2011; Alam and Zhou 2013; Sumner et al. 1999; Sun et al. 2023). The deflection is attributed to the *Coandă* effect: when a jet flow emerges between two side-by-side cylinders, it tends to attach to or align with the surface of the other cylinder. Due to the resulting pressure drop, the flow attempts to sustain this attachment. Thus, a bi-stable behavior (in unsteady conditions, it may change to flip-flop or FF, which depends on P/D and Re (Chen et al. 2022)) is observed.

In C1, the sponges are set closer, thus by forming a central SL and the effects of adjacent sponges on each other, the formation of RBs becomes limited (Fig. S5g). In this condition, the RB of the sponge located in ($X/D = -1, Y/D = 0$) is narrow and triangular in form due to the DF of lateral sponges. Meanwhile, the RB for the sponge located at ($X/D = 3.5, Y/D = 0$) is completely different, as its bubble forms freely and is not under the influence of other sponges' wakes or RBs. After crossing the wave train and changing the wave orbital to a negative direction, RBs form on the mirror side. In this condition, DF and the effects of RBs on each other can be observed. Thus, as observed in previous sections, blocking water and nutrients in the circular pillar is inevitable, as shown in both the velocity diagram and SurfaceLIC.

2. SurfaceLIC at y-z plane

In the next attempt, the SurfaceLIC was used to unravel the vortex structures in the YZ plane across various scenarios. Fig. S6 is dedicated to the depiction. Note that the selected time steps are due to significant flow patterns observed at those times.

Fig. S6. SurfaceLIC plots for the region $X/D = 0$ and $-7.5 \leq Y/D \leq 7.5$ are shown for T1 at (a) $T/10$, (b) $3T/10$, and (c) $5T/10$; for R1 at (d) $T/10$, (e) $3T/10$, and (f) $5T/10$. Plots for the region $X/D = 2$ and $-7.5 \leq Y/D \leq 7.5$ are shown for C1 at (g) $T/10$, (h) $3T/10$, and (i) $5T/10$.

In the YZ plane, two main features can be observed: Counter-Rotating Vortex Pairs (CRVP) and upwelling. It should be noted that due to the transient nature of the wave, these two key phenomena are not detectable at all time steps. Nevertheless, they are considered the primary

features that have a significant impact on marine environments. CRVP can be clearly detected in 5T/10 across all scenarios and is responsible for the major scouring downstream of bluff bodies, thereby enhancing particle suspension (Kundu 2016; Nezu et al. 1985). According to Petersen (2014), CRVP can erode 1.1 times the diameter of a finite-height cylinder. However, the implications extend beyond these observations; as can be observed, the emergence of CRVP leads to splitting the sponges' outflow into two distinct jets, which bend laterally, and a stagnation zone appears at the top of the sponges (shown as SP in Fig. S6a, d, and g). As wave nodes are approached, the local upwelling intensifies (Fig. S6c, f, and i), driving the pumping flow upward. Like natural upwelling, this mechanism can locally enhance vertical momentum exchange, for instance, oxygen and nutrient transport (Liu and Jin 1995). Additionally, this function can influence sediment deposition by increasing vertical particle velocity and buoyancy (Hashempour and Kolahdoozan 2023c). Therefore, despite the sponges' pillar configuration, CRVP and upwelling can still be detected.

3. 3D-stream traces

Three-dimensional stream traces were used to better interpret the dominant flow structures around the bio-mimetic sponge pillars and to complement the 2D SurfaceLIC analysis. Unlike SurfaceLIC, this method allows the identification of complex three-dimensional vortical structures and providing clearer insight into local hydrodynamic behavior. Similar applications of 3D stream traces for hydraulic flow interpretation have also been reported by Palau-Salvador et al. (2010). Figure S8 presents the representative flow structures observed in the three main configurations. In T1, a counter-rotating vortex pair (CRVP) is clearly observed (Fig. S7a), generated by the interaction between wave-induced flow and wake recirculation (Otsuka et al., 2017). This structure promotes vertical transport and contributes to the upward and downward exchange of suspended nutrients and (Park and Park, 2021). In R1, the dominant feature is the formation of a vortex ring, also known as a toroidal vortex (Fig. S7b). This structure is commonly generated when boundary-layer vortices detach at the aperture and evolve into a cylindrical shear layer that curls at its periphery, forming a coherent vortex ring (Francoise et al., 2006; Lim and Nickels, 1995). The vortex ring enhances radial

transport and local mixing, facilitating the displacement of particles and nutrients through its radial velocity component (Munro et al., 2009). Figure S7c shows the formation of a vertical spiral induced by body suction. This structure can lift sediment and nutrients from the bed toward higher-velocity upper regions, followed by downstream advection caused by the expelled flow from the sponge. Figure S7d also illustrates the formation of recirculation bubbles (RBs), which were previously identified in the SurfaceLIC analysis.

Fig. S7. Three-dimensional stream traces showing the dominant flow structures: (a) counter-rotating vortex pair (CRVP) in T1, (b) vortex ring in R1, (c) vertical spiral in R1, and (d) recirculation bubbles (RBs) in C1.

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